

ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT IN MICRO AND SMALL COMPANIES AFTER THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Tássio Mascarenhas de Carvalho – ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7416-919X>.
Doutor e Mestre em Administração das Micro e Pequenas Empresas pela UNIFACCAMP.
Docente do Instituto Federal do Piauí.
E-mail: tassiocarvalho87@gmail.com

Maria Aparecida Sanches - ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1726-9976>. Doutora em Ciências da Saúde na área de Administração Hospitalar pela Universidade Federal de São Paulo /Escola Paulista de Medicina. Mestre em Educação pela Universidade Paulista. Professora pesquisadora da UNIFACCAMP.
E-mail: cidasanches@uol.com.br

Manuel Antonio Meireles da Costa - ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9917-7863>.
Doutor em Ciências pela Universidade Federal de São Paulo/Escola Paulista de Medicina.
Doutor em Engenharia de Produção pela Universidade de São Paulo. Mestre em Administração de Empresas pela Universidade Paulista. Professor pesquisador da UNIFACCAMP
E-mail: meireles@faccamp.br

Abstract

The objective of the article was to analyze organizational commitment in micro and small companies after the Covid-19 pandemic. An explanatory quantitative research was conducted, involving a sample of 414 entrepreneurs working in the city of Teresina-PI. Data collection involved closed-question interviews to gather demographic and occupational information, along with an adapted Likert-type questionnaire on the construct of Organizational Commitment. Descriptive data analysis was performed using the statistical package SPSS version 22.0, and structural equation modeling was conducted using Smart PLS 4.0. Among the entrepreneurs in the Teresina-PI sample, 59.4% had a high school education, 51.4% had been in business for 4 to 9 years, and the majority belonged to the commerce sector, with 22% representing the footwear industry. This research contributes to the scientific knowledge in the field of Administration, as micro and small companies

present an interesting context for understanding the challenges of entrepreneurial action.

Keywords: Organizational Commitment, Covid-19 pandemic, Micro and Small Companies, Entrepreneurs.

1 Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic represented a crisis that impacts many aspects of people's lives worldwide. The most affected countries have implemented various measures such as lockdowns, business closures, hygiene regulations, social distancing, school and university closures, or mobility tracking as a means to slow down the spread of the disease. It has altered the work experience for the vast majority of employees (Hitt et al., 2020).

Research on organizational commitment aims to understand how employee behavior relates to affective, normative, and continuance commitment within micro and small enterprises (MSEs). The Covid-19 pandemic has brought about numerous adverse consequences, including economic shock, a global health crisis, changes in social behaviors, and organizational-level challenges to sustain business operations (Hite & Mcdonald, 2020).

The Covid-19 crisis has created unprecedented demands for immediate and far-reaching organizational changes. To sustainably manage human resources in a balanced and humane manner, reviewing organizational commitment is an appropriate course of action. New information technologies are essential partners for survival and ensuring business sustainability (Hamouche, 2021).

Through a literature review, this study aimed to provide a foundational framework for addressing organizational commitment in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the post-Covid-19 era. The issue concerns the current knowledge gap regarding organizational commitment in Micro and Small Enterprises after the Covid-19 pandemic. The construction of commitment has received significant attention in organizational research for many years. Organizational commitment refers to the extent to which employees perceive themselves as belonging to the

organization. There is still a scarcity of studies regarding organizational commitment in micro and small enterprises after the Covid-19 pandemic. Thus, the research problem was formulated as follows: How does organizational commitment manifest in Micro and Small Enterprises after the Covid-19 pandemic?

This study aims to analyze organizational commitment in Micro and Small Enterprises following the Covid-19 pandemic. The study reflects on the recognition of the role of small businesses in economic development. The connection between the individual and the organization is a widely discussed topic among researchers. Understanding the development, nature, and implications of commitment is arguably more important than ever. The structure and organization that guided this work are presented below.

2 Organizational Commitment

For decades, numerous researchers have focused on the concept of commitment, resulting in a lack of consensus in organizational commitment studies (Mathieu & Zajac, 1990). According to Allen and Meyer (1993), commitment is the psychological bond that connects individuals to an organization, making them less likely to leave the company.

Organizational commitment is associated with a type of bond established between the worker and the company. Meyer & Allen (1993) emphasize that the expectations of both parties are highly specific and individual. An individual may exhibit a combination of commitments at various levels, including commitment to the organization, the work they perform, and the union they are affiliated with. In this context, the unidimensional model developed by Mowday, Steers, and Porter (1979) and the multidimensional model proposed by Meyer (2009) are prominent.

The first internationally recognized publication in the field of organizational commitment measurement was the Organizational Commitment Questionnaire (OCQ) developed by Mowday, Steers, and Porter (1979), which has been widely accepted as a unidimensional construct, capturing emotional attachment to the organization.

In the following decade, in the 1980s, several researchers shifted their focus to different facets and dimensions of commitment. Consequently, within this multidimensional perspective, the Three-Component Model (TCM) by Meyer and Allen (1993) gained significant popularity among researchers and received substantial empirical support for its application.

In international contexts, the fragmentation of measures is rare, and this phenomenon is more pronounced in Brazil. This study addresses the concept that organizational commitment is related to the bond developed between the individual and the organization, as emphasized by Ghosh (2014). In a similar vein, Lizote et al. (2017) highlight that the level of employees' organizational commitment has long been considered a fundamental element for achieving better performance and success for organizations.

It is observed that commitment to the organization occurs when there is an alignment of individual values and goals with those of the organization. The significant research interest in this construct is evident because commitment can impact various attitudes and behaviors that are considered important from an organizational standpoint. These attitudes and behaviors may include attendance, intention to leave the organization, punctuality, response to change, individual and organizational performance, among others.

2.2 Directions of Commitment

Considering that the employee-company bond is complex to understand, the fundamentals of organizational commitment are considered highly valuable for understanding this process as a whole. Consequently, the study proposed by Meyer and Allen (1993) is presented below and it explores three-dimensional models of behavioral studies. It is based on the following: affective, normative, and continuance commitment.

While there are various models to conceptualize the constituent parts of the alliance, one extensively researched and internationally accepted model has been confirmed in numerous cultures. As mentioned in the concept of mindset, it can be said that each dimension of engagement is associated with a mindset. For example, the

dimensions (or foundations) of organizational commitment mainly differ due to the psychological nature of each one.

In terms of the history of Design studies, Mowday, Steers, and Porter (1979) approached Design in a unidimensional manner. This was dominated by a method known as emotional or behavioral attachment to the organization. Since the 1990s, multidimensional frameworks have been discussed, shifting away from a strictly unidimensional perspective and moving beyond solely emotional or behavioral approaches.

2.2.1 Affective Commitment

Mowday et al. (1979) define affective commitment as "a state in which an individual identifies with a particular organization and its goals, and desires to remain a member of it." Mowday (1998) emphasizes that as employees perceive the organization's commitment to them, their affective bond with the organization tends to strengthen.

Mowday et al. (1979, p. 226) emphasize that affective commitment also presupposes a worker's identification with the organization. According to Meyer (1993), the formation of affective commitment comprises: a) belief and acceptance of organizational goals and values, b) willingness to exert effort on behalf of the organization, and c) desire to remain in the organization. When an employee internalizes the company's values through identification with its goals, an affective bond emerges. Mathieu and Zajac (1990) address that the effects of affective commitment are associated with higher performance levels.

2.2.2 Normative Commitment

Normative commitment, on the other hand, can be understood as a sense of moral debt, duty, or moral obligation on the part of the worker towards the organization. Wiener and Vardi (1980) employed the concept of organizational culture and motivation. Culture is defined as the set of shared values that impose normative

pressures on individuals. Individuals who possess this type of commitment recognize that they remain in the organization out of a sense of obligation and moral duty.

Allen and Meyer (1990) developed the first scale to measure normative commitment, aiming to provide evidence for the conceptualization of the three components of organizational commitment. In 1991, the authors presented a validated model recognized by the literature on the subject.

2.2.3 Continuance Commitment

Continuance Commitment can be understood based on the contributions of Becker (1960), who introduced the theory of side-bets. In this theory, individuals evaluate how much they have invested in their relationship with the organization in terms of time, effort, and money. Based on this analysis, they decide whether breaking the bond would be advantageous or not.

Scales to measure instrumental commitment were operationalized by Ritzer and Trice (1969) and by Hrebiniak and Alluto (1972). Meyer and Allen (1984) developed a scale that assesses instrumental commitment by evaluating the perceived costs associated with leaving the organization.

2.3 Multidimensional Models of Commitment

The most widely accepted model in the academic field was proposed by Meyer and Allen (1993). It is argued that few inconsistent studies have been conducted to test the relationship between the three types of commitment. It is suggested that there is overlap between affective and normative commitments. The sense of reciprocity can be accompanied by an emotional attachment to the organization. Various models with multidimensional approaches to organizational commitment demonstrate the evolution of the concepts that make up the construct. The model proposed by Jaros et al. (1993) represents a significant advancement in the field of multidimensional research on commitment.

3 Method

The objective of the study is to analyze, through cross-sectional studies, the composition of organizational obligations based on the perceptions of small and medium-sized business owners in Teresina, specifically those registered with SEBRAE-PI - Teresina. Therefore, this research is characterized as a quantitative survey study. In terms of objectives, Creswell (2017) highlights that research can be classified as exploratory, descriptive, and explanatory. In this regard, the research is descriptive as it aims to analyze the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the organizational commitment of small and medium-sized businesses registered in the SEBRAE-PI database.

3.1 Population and Sample

The target audience consisted of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) in Teresina-PI, registered in the database of SEBRAE-PI. The sample comprised 414 randomly selected micro and small business owners who had been in business for more than five years. To obtain research authorization, the research project proposal was submitted to SEBRAE-PI.

3.2 Organizational Commitment Questionnaire

The Expert Panel Method was used to obtain the face validity of the Organizational Commitment Questionnaire. The critical judgment of experts helps improve the construction of questionnaires, enhancing the quality of data collection and, consequently, the research results. The selection of experts is based on peer recognition and knowledge in the field of study. Five analysts in the field of Entrepreneurship and Innovation were invited to participate in this Expert Panel. After receiving their feedback, adjustments to the questionnaire were made based on their suggestions for improvement.

3.3 Research Instrument

The interview began with closed-ended questions about demographic and occupational data. The second stage of the interview used an adapted questionnaire on the construct of Organizational Commitment. The questionnaire on organizational commitment was constructed based on Meyer & Allen's (1993) three-dimensional model. The questionnaire consists of 15 items, of which 6 are negatively polarized.

3.4 Data collection

The management of SEBRAE-PI in Teresina, Brazil supported the research by granting permission for its conduct. The questionnaire was administered both in person and online. Data collection started on February 8, 2023, and concluded on March 18, 2023. An online instrument hosted on the Google Docs platform was used for data collection, as well as printed questionnaires according to the convenience and preference of the participants.

Out of the 414 obtained responses, 285 were collected in person, with the researchers approaching the owners of Micro and Small Enterprises. A total of 242 online questionnaires and 43 printed questionnaires were used, based on the preference of the respondents or when internet access was not available at the location.

3.5 Data Analysis

This research analyzed and tested the model that employed Organizational Commitment based on the perception of small and medium-sized business owners in the city-state of Teresina-PI. The validated and adapted questionnaire from Meyer and Allen (1993) was used in Likert scale format to analyze the organizational role of micro and small businesses. To assess the level of organizational effort, the statistical package SPSS 22.0 was used for descriptive data analysis, and Smart PLS 4.0 was used for structural equation modeling (Stehlik-Barry; Babinec, 2017).

4 Analysis and Results

In this section, the data is analyzed and the results are discussed, presented statistically, correlating the theory and Organizational Commitment as perceived by the entrepreneurs. The field research results were analyzed through applied questionnaires. The graphs and tables presented in this section were created based on the tables.

4.1 Respondents' Profile

The profile of the study respondents was outlined based on their responses to questions regarding gender, age group, marital status, education level, length of service, position in the company, economic sector, and industry.

There was a balance between 210 female respondents (50.7%) and 204 male respondents (49.3%) in the sample. According to the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) research (2019), it was estimated that, in Brazil, entrepreneurs are divided equally between men (50.0%) and women (50.0%). Regarding the age range of the respondents, there was a predominance of individuals aged between 34 and 41 years, accounting for (63.0%) of the respondents.

Regarding the length of service of the respondents, a significant portion had been with their companies for five to nine years, accounting for (51.4%), followed by individuals with ten to fourteen years of service (41.5%). As for the company classification, the results showed that 84.5% of the entrepreneurs owned a Microenterprise (ME), followed by 11.8% who were Microentrepreneurs (MEI), and 3.6% who were owners of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). In terms of the economic sector of the companies, a significant portion belonged to the Commerce sector (77.5%), followed by the Services sector (21.0%). A balanced distribution was noticed in the sample regarding the industry of the researched companies. Footwear companies had a slightly higher occurrence (22.0%), followed by clothing companies (17.6%). The least prominent industries were stationery and others, accounting for 17.4% of the analyzed sample.

The analysis of quantitative data regarding the sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents was conducted based on the personal information provided in the

electronic questionnaire. The variables analyzed allowed for a brief and clear characterization of the sample in terms of gender, age group, educational level, and marital status.

4.2 Analysis of Constructs

In this stage of the study, the results of the indicators obtained in the analysis of the constructs comprising the tested model are presented as follows: each indicator measured in the construct is presented, followed by the number of responses for each item. Additionally, descriptive statistics are provided, including mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, skewness, and kurtosis. Skewness and kurtosis indices were used to assess indications of distribution normality.

4.2.1 Affective Commitment

Affective commitment refers to the deep emotional attachment that employees establish with the organization. When employees are emotionally committed, they are more willing to dedicate themselves to tasks and responsibilities. They are willing to go above and beyond to contribute to the organization's success because they feel emotionally connected to it (Mowday, Steers, & Porter, 1979).

The descriptive statistics for the affective commitment construct are presented in Table 1, showing the results for the six assessed items.

Table 1 - Descriptive Statistics of the Affective Commitment Construct

N 414	Scale					Descriptive Statistics				
	1	2	3	4	5	Mean	s. d.	C.V.	Skew.	Kurt.
Comm1	0,2	1,0	4,8	35,0	58,9	4,51	,659	,434	-1,430	2,724
Comm2	-	0,7	4,3	37,0	58,0	4,52	,617	,381	-1,108	1,072
Comm3	50,7	40,1	5,6	1,9	1,7	1,64	,814	,663	1,728	4,032

Comm5	0,7	0,7	6,6	39,4	52,7		4,43	,712	,506	-1,435	3,272
Comm6	0,2	-	5,8	40,8	53,1		4,47	,628	,395	-,990	1,410
Comm14	0,2	1,2	8,0	40,1	50,5		4,39	,708	,501	-1,102	1,421

Based on the frequency analysis of the data, it is evident that affective commitment occurs in all items. There is a higher concentration of responses towards the higher end of the scale. Item two of the affective commitment scale ("I believe that employees are more likely to recommend my company to their friends as a place to work") yielded a significant result (mean = 4.52) on the second-order affective commitment construct scale. It is worth noting that item three ("I believe that employees today have less loyalty to the company than before") is reverse-coded, and prior to data analysis, in which an adjustment was made.

The obtained means suggest that the respondents evaluated affective commitment positively, as the means are above 4.00. However, it is noticeable that the standard deviation and coefficient of variation for the items showed little variation, indicating lower data dispersion.

4.2.2 Normative Commitment

Normative commitment reflects a moral and ethical obligation that employees feel towards the organization. Individuals with a high degree of this type of commitment feel a strong obligation to remain with the organization, even if they have better opportunities elsewhere (Meyer et al., 2013).

The results of the descriptive statistics for the normative commitment construct are presented in Table 2, for the five assessed items.

Table 2 - Descriptive Statistics of the Normative Commitment Construct

N 414	Scale	Descriptive Statistics
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	1	2	3	4	5		Mea n	s. d.	C.V.	Skew.	Kurt.
Comm7	0,7	2,2	10, 1	37, 7	49, 3		4,33	,80 1	,642	-1,253	1,779
Comm8	0,5	0,7	4,3	38, 9	55, 6		4,48	,66 3	,439	-1,468	3,610
Comm9	50, 2	37, 9	8,2	1,7	1,9		1,67	,84 8	,720	1,616	3.319
Comm1 2	49, 0	40, 8	6,8	2,2	1,2		1,66	,79 8	,638	1,528	3,186
Comm1 3	0,5	1,0	4,8	36, 2	57, 5		4,49	,68 1	,464	-1,546	3,561

Based on the frequency analysis of the data, it can be observed that normative commitment occurred in all the items. It is noteworthy that the items "comp 9" (I believe that employees today are more likely to easily change companies than before) and "comp 12" (I believe that employees today have more difficulties than before in agreeing with the company's policies on important issues concerning them) from the scale used for normative commitment had their signs reversed, and adjustments were made before analyzing the data. On the other hand, it is evident that items eight (I believe that employees today perform their best more than before in terms of job performance) and thirteen (I believe that employees today care more than before about the fate of the company) from the scale used for normative commitment yielded highly significant results (averages above 4.40) in the second-order normative commitment construct scale.

The obtained means suggest that respondents evaluated normative commitment positively, as the averages exceeded 4.00. However, it is observed that the standard deviation and coefficient of variation of the items showed little variation, indicating lower data dispersion.

4.2.3 Continuance Commitment

This form of commitment is related to the perception that employees have much to lose if they decide to leave the organization. It is essential for organizations to understand employees' commitment to continuity and find a balance to retain valuable talents (Meyer et al., 2013).

The results of the descriptive statistics for the continuance commitment construct will be presented in Table 3, including the four evaluated items.

Table 3 - Descriptive Statistics of the Continuance Commitment Construct

N 414	Scale					Descriptive Statistics				
	1	2	3	4	5	Mean	s.d.	C.V.	Skew.	Kurt.
Comm4	0,7	-	4,8	37,9	56,5	4,50	,659	,435	-1,562	4,422
Comm10	0,5	0,5	7,1	39,1	52,7	4,43	,691	,478	-1,248	2,357
Comm11	54,8	37,0	5,8	1,9	0,5	1,56	,733	,537	1,487	2,870
Comm15	53,1	38,6	6,8	0,7	0,7	1,57	,715	,512	1,438	3,204

Upon analyzing the frequency data, it can be observed that continuance commitment was present in all the items. It is evident that the items "comp 9" (I believe that employees today would change companies more easily than before) and "comp 12" (I believe that employees today have more difficulty than before in agreeing with the company's policies on important matters concerning them) from the scale used for continuance commitment had their signs reversed, and adjustments were made before analyzing the data. On the other hand, items eight (I believe that employees today perform their best more than before in terms of job performance) and thirteen (I believe that employees today care more than before about the fate of the company) from the scale used for continuance commitment showed highly significant results (averages above 4.40) in the second-order construct scale of continuance commitment.

The obtained means suggest that respondents evaluated continuance commitment positively, since averages above 4.00 emerged. However, it is noticeable that the standard deviation and coefficient of variation of the items showed little variation, indicating lower data dispersion.

4.3 Likert Scale Analysis using Scarpi's Aggregative

Furthermore, an analysis of the responses was conducted using Scarpi's Aggregative approach in order to "obtain levels of adherence or agreement to a proposition (or item or statement) or a factor" (Scarpi, 2010, p. 548). The equation for Scarpi's Aggregative is presented in Equation (1), where s represents the number of scale positions, q_i represents the number of observations for a particular position, and QT represents the total number of responses obtained for the proposition.

Equation (1): Aggregative of Scarpi

$$(1) \quad GA_{SCARPI} = 100 \left(\frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^s q_i \right) - QT}{(s-1)QT} \right)$$

The responses were analyzed using Scarpi's Aggregative approach for each dimension separately, namely: Affective Commitment, Normative Commitment, and Continuance Commitment. Initially, the Scarpi's Aggregative was analyzed for the Affective Commitment construct. The results demonstrate that the items on the Likert scale showed an aggregative that could represent a very strong agreement for items one and two. For items three, five, six, and fourteen, a substantial agreement was observed (Meireles, 2020; Scarpi, 2010), as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 - Scarpi's Aggregative for Affective Commitment Construct

Affective commitment	Semantic differential					QT	GAScar pi	Dp	Cp
	1	2	3	4	5				
	TD	D	I	A	TA				
Factor – Organizational commitment									
I believe that my employees today are more willing than ever to strive and do their best beyond expectations to help the company succeed.	1	4	20	145	244	414	87,86	15.00	399.00
I believe that employees recommend my company to their friends to work	0	3	18	153	240	414	88.04	12.00	402.00

with, more than ever before.									
I believe that employees today have little loyalty to the company than they once did.	210	166	23	8	7	414	15.94	387.50	26.50
I believe that today, more than ever before, employee values are similar to company values.	3	3	27	163	218	414	85.63	19.50	394.50
I believe that today my employees are prouder than before to say that they work for the company.	1	0	24	169	220	414	86.65	13.00	401.00
I believe that employees today think the company is the best place they have ever worked, more than before.	1	5	33	166	209	414	84.84	22.50	391.50
Factor	216	181	145	804	1.138	2.484	94.79	469.50	2014.50

For the Normative Commitment construct, the results showed a level of Scarpi's Aggregative tending towards a very strong agreement for items eight and thirteen. Additionally, a substantial level of agreement was observed for items seven, nine, and twelve on the Likert scale used in the study (Meireles, 2020; Scarpi, 2010), as shown in Table 5.

Table 5 - Scarpi's Aggregative for Normative Commitment Construct

Normative commitment	Semantic differential					QT	GAScar pi	Dp	Cp
	1	2	3	4	5				
	TD	D	I	A	TA				
Factor – Organizational commitment									
I believe that today employees would work in other companies as long as the type of activity is similar to that of my company.	3	9	42	156	204	414	83.15	33.00	381.00
I believe that today employees perform their best more than before in terms of job performance.	2	3	18	161	230	414	87.08	14.00	400.00
I believe that today more employees than before would easily change companies.	208	157	34	7	8	414	16.79	382.00	32.00

I believe that employees today have more difficulty than ever before in agreeing with company policies on important matters concerning them.	203	169	28	9	5	414	16.43	386.00	28.00
I believe that today employees care more than before about the company's destiny.	2	4	20	150	238	414	87.32	16.00	398.00
Factor	418	340	138	479	693	2.070	58.25	831.00	1239.00

According to the results of Scarpi's Aggregative, the Continuance Commitment construct showed a very strong agreement for item four on the tested scale and a substantial agreement for items ten, eleven, and fifteen on the Likert scale (Meireles, 2020; Scarpi, 2010), as shown in Table 6.

Table 6 - Scarpi's Aggregative for Continuance Commitment Construct

Continuance commitment	Semantic differential					QT	GAScarpi	Dp	Cp
	1	2	3	4	5				
	TD	D	I	A	TA				
Factor – Organizational commitment									
I believe that today employees would accept other tasks more than before to keep working for the company.	3	0	20	157	234	414	87.38	13.00	401.00
I believe that employees today are happier than before because they chose my company, when they joined, over others.	2	2	30	162	218	414	85.75	19.00	395.00
I believe that today employees do not expect to earn more than before by staying at the company indefinitely.	227	153	24	8	2	414	14.07	392.00	22.00
I believe that today, more than before, employees think that working at my company was a bad decision.	220	160	28	3	3	414	14.31	394.00	20.00
Factor	452	315	102	330	457	1.656	50.37	818.00	838.00

The next topic addresses the analysis of the structural model in the research.

4.4 Analysis of the Structural Model in the Research

Regarding reliability, it is important to highlight that all constructs in the study demonstrated satisfactory indicators of extracted variance analysis (AVE) above 0.50, composite reliability, and Cronbach's Alpha above 0.70 (Hair et al., 2014), as presented in Table 14.

The analysis of extracted variance (AVE) is a measure that indicates the proportion of variance in a construct captured by its indicators. Values above 0.50 indicate that more than half of the construct's variance is being explained by its indicators, which is considered a good reliability index. Furthermore, composite reliability is a measure that assesses the internal consistency of a construct, taking into account the correlation between the indicators. Values above 0.70 indicate that the indicators are consistently measuring the construct in question.

Cronbach's Alpha is another measure used to evaluate the internal reliability of a set of items. Values above 0.70 indicate good internal consistency, meaning that the items are adequately correlated with each other. Therefore, based on the criteria established by Hair et al. (2014), the constructs in the study demonstrated satisfactory reliability indicators, indicating that the items used to measure each construct are reliable and consistent.

It is important to emphasize that the reliability of the constructs is crucial to ensure the validity and accuracy of the results obtained in the study. A reliable measure allows researchers to have greater confidence in the results and the conclusions that can be inferred from the collected data.

In summary, the reliability indicators, such as extracted variance analysis (AVE), composite reliability, and Cronbach's Alpha, were satisfactory for all constructs in the study, as shown in Table 7. These results reinforce the reliability of the items used to measure the constructs and provide a solid foundation for the analysis and interpretation of the collected data.

Table 7 - Reliability Indicators of the Constructs

	AVE	Composite reliability
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Affective commitment	0.765	0.939
Continuance commitment	0.713	0.866
Normative commitment	0.708	0.898
Organizational commitment	0.688	0.968

Considering that the square roots of AVEs were not greater than the correlation coefficient between latent variables, it can be concluded that there is a lack of discriminant validity among the analyzed constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), as shown in Table 15.

Discriminant validity is a measure that assesses whether the constructs in a study are distinct from one another. It is important to establish discriminant validity to ensure that the constructs are measuring unique aspects of the phenomenon under investigation and are not overlapping or redundant.

In the present study, the analysis of discriminant validity was based on the comparison between the square roots of the AVEs and the correlation coefficients between the latent variables. According to Fornell and Larcker (1981), if the square root of the AVE for a construct is smaller than the correlation coefficient between that construct and other constructs, it indicates a lack of discriminant validity.

In Table 8, the results indicate that the square roots of the AVEs were not greater than the correlation coefficients for the analyzed constructs. This suggests that there is an overlap or similarity between the constructs, and they are not sufficiently distinct from each other. Consequently, it raises concerns about the discriminant validity of the constructs.

It is important to address the issue of discriminant validity in future research to ensure that the constructs are properly defined and distinct from one another. This could involve revisiting the measurement items, exploring alternative conceptualizations, or considering additional constructs to capture the unique aspects of the phenomenon.

Table 8 - Discriminant Validity Assessment of the Constructs

	Affectiv e	Continuanc e	Normativ e	Organization al
Affective commitment	0.875			
Continuance commitment	0.902	0.845		
Normative commitment	0.913	0.914		
Organizational commitment	0.976	0.960	0.841 0.970	0.830

To assess discriminant validity, an additional criterion based on variance analysis was employed, following the approach proposed by Henseler, Ringle, and Sarstedt (2015). This criterion is known as heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT), which utilizes correlations to evaluate the distinction between constructs (Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015).

Upon analyzing the obtained results, it was found that the values for HTMT were not statistically significant, as all the values exceeded 0.85 (Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015), as demonstrated in Table 9.

The use of HTMT is an important approach to assess discriminant validity as it allows for examining the relationship between distinct constructs and measuring the degree of distinction between them. Values below 0.85 are generally considered as evidence of acceptable discriminant validity, indicating that the constructs are measuring distinct characteristics and are not highly correlated. However, the results obtained in this study revealed values above this threshold, suggesting an overlap or high correlation between the constructs. This may indicate a possible lack of distinction among the evaluated constructs or the presence of some conceptual overlap.

These results should be taken into consideration when interpreting the study data and drawing conclusions based on them. The lack of discriminant validity among the constructs may limit the ability to differentiate them and could have implications for result interpretation and study conclusions.

In summary, the HTMT criterion based on variance analysis was utilized to assess the discriminant validity of the constructs. However, the results indicated values above 0.85, suggesting a possible lack of distinction among the evaluated constructs.

Table 9 - Discriminant Validity by Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) Criterion

	Affective	Continuance	Normative	Organizational
Affective commitment				
Continuance commitment	1.000			
Normative commitment	0.995	1.035		
Organizational commitment	1.023	1.049	1.042	

To assess the adequacy of the model regarding the analyzed endogenous constructs (Rigdon, 2012), evaluations of effect sizes (f^2) and (q^2), as well as predictive relevance (Q^2), were conducted. The calculation of f^2 follows the approach proposed by Hair Jr. et al. (2014) (Equation 1):

$$f^2 = \frac{R^2_{\text{included}} - R^2_{\text{deleted}}}{1 - R^2_{\text{included}}} \quad (1)$$

Additionally, the analysis of Q^2 values, based on the omission distance (OD) of 5 to 10, is widely recommended as an analytical approach for most research studies (Hair et al., 2012). The estimated Q^2 and q^2 values from the blindfolding procedure represent a measure of how well the path model is able to predict the initially observed values and the relative impact of predictive relevance, respectively.

The analysis of effect sizes (f^2) is important for understanding the magnitude of relationships between variables in the model. Higher f^2 values indicate that an independent variable has a substantially larger effect on the dependent variable, thus contributing to explaining the variability of that dependent variable.

The formula for calculating q^2 is:

$$q^2 = \frac{Q^2_{\text{included}} - Q^2_{\text{deleted}}}{1 - Q^2_{\text{included}}} \quad (2)$$

The Q^2 and q^2 values provide information about the predictive ability of the path model. Q^2 measures the overall predictive power of the model, indicating how well it is able to predict the observed values. Positive values of Q^2 suggest a good predictive power of the model. On the other hand, q^2 measures the predictive

relevance of a specific variable within the model, providing a measure of how well that variable contributes to the prediction of the observed values.

Therefore, by analyzing the effect sizes (f^2) and the Q^2 and q^2 values, it is possible to assess the adequacy of the model in terms of its explanatory and predictive capabilities. These measures are important for understanding the validity and reliability of the path model used in the research. Table 10 presents the results for the f^2 and q^2 indices.

Table 10 - Results for the f^2 and q^2 indices.

f^2 indices of the analyzed constructs				
	R² included	R² deleted	f^2 effect	Size
Affective commitment			0.665	Big
Normative commitment			0.512	Big
Continuance commitment			0.555	Big
q^2 indices of the analyzed constructs				
	Q² included	Q² deleted	q² effect	Size
Affective commitment			0.723	Big
Normative commitment			0.651	Big
Continuance commitment			0.662	Big

The first-order constructs - affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment - played a significant role in defining organizational commitment in the analyzed companies (Hair et al., 2014). These constructs represent different aspects of individuals' commitment to the organization.

To assess the relevance of the tested model, we can consider Q^2 , as suggested by Chin (2000). Q^2 is a measure that indicates how well the model is able to make predictions beyond the observed data. Positive values of Q^2 indicate that the model has predictive relevance, meaning it is capable of making reasonably accurate predictions.

The model was able to make predictions greater than zero, indicating its ability to explain and predict organizational commitment in the analyzed companies. This finding contributes to theoretical and practical knowledge, providing insights into the factors that influence individuals' commitment to organizations. The first-order

constructs used in the model were relevant and had a significant impact on understanding organizational commitment.

In summary, the first-order constructs - affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment - were significant in defining organizational commitment in the analyzed companies. Additionally, a predictive relevance of the tested model was observed, as evidenced by Q^2 being greater than zero. These findings reinforce the importance of these constructs in understanding organizational commitment and provide theoretical support for the field of organizational studies.

The obtained results demonstrated the relevance of the first-order constructs - affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment - in explaining organizational commitment. The analysis of the structural model revealed that all these constructs had significant effects on organizational commitment.

For affective commitment, a β coefficient of 0.976, a t-value of 181.51, and a p-value <0.01 were observed. This indicates that affective commitment had a substantial and positive influence on organizational commitment, being statistically significant.

Similarly, normative commitment also proved to be relevant in explaining organizational commitment. The β coefficient was 0.970, the t-value was 139.071, and the p-value <0.01 . These results indicate that normative commitment had a significant and positive impact on organizational commitment.

Continuance commitment was also considered relevant in explaining organizational commitment, with a β coefficient of 0.960, a t-value of 100.054, and a p-value <0.01 . This means that continuance commitment had a significant and positive influence on organizational commitment. These results are visualized in Figures 1 and 2, which present the structural model with the values of the first-order constructs and the results of the Student's t-test (bootstrapping).

In summary, the results highlight the importance of the first-order constructs - affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment - in explaining organizational commitment. These constructs demonstrated significant and positive effects on organizational commitment, as evidenced by the β

coefficients, t-values, and p-values obtained. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the factors that influence individuals' commitment to organizations.

Organizational commitment is composed of different dimensions, represented by first-order constructs such as affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment. In the context of the present study, where all dimensions are related to the same object - organizational commitment - it is expected that there would be interconnectedness and a lack of discriminant validity among these dimensions.

This multidimensional approach provides a broader and more in-depth view of organizational commitment, considering its different facets and highlighting the importance of each dimension for its understanding. These results have significant implications for organizational theory and practice, enabling a better understanding of the factors that influence individuals' commitment and providing insights for people management strategies and strengthening the relationship between employees and the organization.

Figure 1 - Structural model of the research

According to Figure 1, it can be observed that the three dimensions related to organizational commitment (affective, continuance, normative) are significant in shaping the organizational commitment of the small and medium-sized companies

analyzed. It is worth noting that the bootstrapping analysis confirms the structural model of the research, as shown in Figure 2.

Upon analyzing Figure 2, it can be seen that the T-value exceeds 1.96, indicating statistical significance at a confidence level of $p \leq 0.01$. This leads us to conclude that, for the companies analyzed in this study, affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment play a significant role in explaining organizational commitment.

Based on the presented results, it can be stated that affective commitment may account for approximately 95.2% of organizational commitment, as indicated by $R^2 = 0.952$. This highlights that employees' emotional attachment to the organization has a considerable influence on overall commitment to the company.

Figure 2 - Research Bootstrapping

Similarly, continuance commitment can account for approximately 92.2% of organizational commitment, as indicated by $R^2 = 0.922$. This suggests that employees' motivation to avoid costs and risks associated with potential employer changes plays a significant role in their dedication to the organization.

Furthermore, normative commitment can represent approximately 94.2% of organizational commitment, as indicated by $R^2 = 0.942$. This suggests that employees' moral and ethical obligations towards the organization exert a strong influence on overall commitment to the company.

These findings have relevant implications for people management in organizations. They highlight the need to promote a work environment that fosters employees' emotional attachment and a sense of moral and ethical obligation. By recognizing the importance of these factors, companies can develop strategies to strengthen employee commitment, enhance their satisfaction, and improve performance.

4.5 Discussion of Results

The results obtained in this research belong to a specific context, namely, Micro and Small Enterprises after the Covid-19 pandemic in the city of Teresina-PI. Therefore, the results may not be generalizable to other geographical regions or different time periods. These limitations emphasize the need for future studies that include a more diverse sample.

Out of the surveyed entrepreneurs, 50.7% were female, indicating a significant presence of women in business leadership positions. The majority of owners (63.0%) were between 34 and 41 years old, which suggests that this age group plays a prominent role in managing SMEs.

The majority of owners of the analyzed SMEs were in a marital union. As for education, 59.4% of owners had completed high school. The lack of more advanced educational background may have an impact on the access to resources and strategies that could contribute to the development and growth of SMEs. 84.5% of the surveyed entrepreneurs owned Microenterprises (MEs), and 51.4% of owners indicated that their companies had been operating for five to nine years. This suggests that these SMEs are in an intermediate phase of their business trajectory, which may imply specific challenges and opportunities.

It is important to mention that the demographic and occupational profile of the owners of the analyzed SMEs in this research may not represent all realities and

business contexts. Aspects such as prior experience in the business sector, motivations for entrepreneurship, economic and cultural context, among others, may also play an important role in how owners commit to their organizations.

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of this research in relation to its exclusive focus on SME owners. If the research also included employees of the company, it would be possible to obtain a more comprehensive and comparative view of organizational commitment. Employees' opinions may differ from those of owners, reflecting different perceptions and experiences in the work environment. Future research may seek to include more diverse samples, encompassing both owners and employees.

There was a tendency for a greater concentration of responses in the higher categories of the scale, indicating that SME owners exhibited a considerable level of commitment in these dimensions. The average values were above 4.00, suggesting that entrepreneurs perceive and recognize the importance of these types of commitment.

These findings indicate the presence of a favorable scenario of commitment in the studied SMEs, with a higher propensity of entrepreneurs to exhibit emotional engagement, moral obligation, and motivation to avoid costs associated with employer change. However, it is worth noting that the homogeneity of responses may limit the generalization of the results to other SMEs or different contexts.

The results demonstrate the relevance of affective, normative, and continuance commitment as indicators of organizational behavior in SMEs after the Covid-19 pandemic. Nevertheless, it is essential to consider the aforementioned aspects, as well as the need for further studies encompassing a more diverse sample.

The constructs evaluated in this study demonstrated satisfactory reliability, according to the indicators used, such as the Extracted Variance Analysis (AVE), composite reliability, and Cronbach's Alpha. The AVE, which assesses the proportion of item variance captured by the construct, yielded values above 0.50 for all constructs, indicating good ability of the items to measure the desired construct.

The correlation between questionnaire items was also examined, and a significant correlation was found among them. This result strengthens the construct validity, as

the positive correlation between items indicates that they adequately measure the intended construct.

Furthermore, the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient was calculated for each construct and ranged from 0.866 to 0.968. These results demonstrate that the Organizational Commitment Questionnaire used in the research has high internal consistency and reliability, as the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient exceeds the recommended minimum threshold of 0.70.

It is noteworthy that the Cronbach's Alpha values obtained in this research surpass the results of a previous study that validated the same organizational commitment scale, where values ranged from 0.82 to 0.93 (Mowday et al., 1992). This comparison further reinforces the reliability of the constructs measured in this study.

The affective, normative, and continuance commitment constructs used in this study exhibit high reliability and are capable of consistently and accurately measuring the dimensions of organizational commitment. These findings support the validity and robustness of the research instrument used, providing greater confidence in the obtained results, say the authors.

It is worth highlighting that the reliabilities of other scales on Organizational Commitment are verified through the assessment of Cronbach's Alpha, in most studies (Bastos et al., 2011; Bastos & Aguiar, 2015).

In the process of analyzing the structural model of this research, different criteria were employed to evaluate the model specification and the relevance of the analyzed endogenous constructs. In this regard, the effect sizes (f^2) and (q^2), as well as predictive relevance (Q^2), were considered.

These findings point to the existence of a favorable scenario of commitment in the studied SMEs, with a higher tendency of entrepreneurs to manifest emotional engagement, moral obligation, and motivation to avoid costs associated with employer change. However, it is worth noting that the homogeneity of responses may limit the generalization of the results to other SMEs or different contexts.

The results show the relevance of affective, normative, and continuance commitment as indicators of organizational behavior in SMEs after the Covid-19 pandemic.

However, it is essential to consider the aforementioned aspects, as well as the need for further studies encompassing a more diverse sample.

The effect sizes (f^2) were evaluated for each construct in relation to organizational commitment. It was observed that all constructs exhibited an f^2 effect above 0.35, which is considered a large effect. These results indicate that the three dimensions of commitment (affective, normative, and continuance) indeed play a significant role in explaining organizational commitment. This finding reinforces the importance of these dimensions as essential components of organizational commitment.

Furthermore, the predictive relevance of the model (Q^2) was also examined. The value of Q^2 should be greater than 0.5 to indicate a well-fitting and correct model. The obtained results revealed values of 0.7 for affective commitment, 0.6 for normative commitment, and 0.6 for continuance commitment. These non-zero numbers indicate that the model is appropriate, as the commitment dimensions can predict the observed values in a relevant manner.

The commitment dimensions (affective, normative, and continuance) have a strong effect on explaining organizational commitment. Additionally, the model demonstrated good predictive relevance. These findings contribute to the validation and robustness of the proposed model in this research. They strengthen the understanding of the relationship between commitment dimensions and organizational commitment.

The first-order constructs of affective commitment, normative commitment, and continuance commitment were significant in defining the organizational commitment of the analyzed companies (Hair et al., 2014). Chin (2000) suggests that a good model demonstrates relevance when Q^2 is greater than 0.5. Therefore, the existence of predictive relevance of the tested model was noted.

Affective commitment was relevant in explaining organizational commitment ($\beta=0.976$; $t\text{-value}=181.51$; $p<0.01$). Normative commitment was also relevant in explaining organizational commitment ($\beta=0.970$; $p<0.01$). Finally, continuance commitment was relevant in explaining organizational commitment ($\beta=0.960$; $p<0.01$). Thus, it can be observed that the three dimensions related to organizational

commitment (affective, continuance, and normative) are significant in the formation of organizational commitment in the analyzed small and medium-sized enterprises.

Overall, commitment - particularly affective commitment - proves to be an important construct in organizational commitment research. Thus, in the perception of Micro and Small Business owners, the degree to which employees feel connected to their organization correlates significantly with important variables related to performance-related behavior. From the organization's perspective, the interest is therefore to promote high commitment from employees (Kanning & Hill, 2013).

After the Covid-19 pandemic, it becomes evident that these three factors play a significant role in managers' perception of companies. Affective commitment, in particular, is generally assessed at high levels by managers. This indicates that employees develop an emotional bond and identification with the organization.

According to Meyer and Allen (1993), affective commitment reflects the emotional connection and identification of the employee with the organization. Normative commitment, on the other hand, suggests that the decision to remain in employment is based on a perceived obligation by the employee. Lastly, continuance commitment is related to awareness of the costs involved in leaving the organization, implying that staying is considered necessary.

It would be relevant to conduct research that includes the perspective of employees as well. This would allow for a more comprehensive and comparative analysis of managers' and employees' perceptions. It would provide a fuller understanding of organizational commitment in the context of Micro and Small Businesses after the Covid-19 pandemic.

When analyzing the responses obtained in the questionnaires answered by Micro and Small Business owners, a high level of affective commitment from employees towards their companies was observed. This result contradicts the conclusions of a previous study conducted by La Falce et al. (2017), in which the authors argued that affective commitment was decreasing over time in studies on the subject.

This finding reveals the importance of considering the specificities of the context in which the research was conducted. It can be inferred that in the analyzed

companies, there was a strengthening of the emotional bond and identification of employees with their organizations, even in a post-Covid-19 pandemic scenario.

However, it is crucial to keep in mind that these conclusions are based on the perceptions collected from business owners, which may introduce a bias in the responses. To obtain a more comprehensive understanding of employees' affective commitment, it would be valuable to conduct additional studies that also involve the perspective of the employees themselves. This would allow for a comparative and more complete analysis of perceptions about affective commitment in Micro and Small Businesses, contributing to a deeper understanding of this dynamic and its variations over time.

The last specific objective of this research aimed to describe commitment in Micro and Small Businesses in the post-Covid-19 pandemic context. The obtained results revealed a high level of organizational commitment from employees, encompassing the dimensions proposed by Meyer and Allen (1993).

These results provide valuable insights into the dynamics of organizational commitment in a particularly challenging context, such as the post-Covid-19 pandemic period. It demonstrates the importance of promoting strategies that strengthen employee commitment, such as engagement initiatives, recognition, and appreciation of internal talents. Additionally, managers can benefit from adopting people management practices that foster a sense of belonging, mutual trust, and alignment with the organization's goals and values.

However, it is relevant to highlight that the results of this study are based on the perceptions collected from Micro and Small Business owners. For a comprehensive understanding of organizational commitment in this context, future research could explore additional perspectives, such as those of employees and customers, in order to obtain a more complete and contextualized view of the phenomenon. This would contribute to a deeper understanding of the factors driving and sustaining organizational commitment in Micro and Small Businesses, enabling the development of more effective people management strategies and gaining a competitive advantage.

In the face of these challenges, it is crucial for companies to adopt policies and practices that promote employee commitment and satisfaction. This may include implementing work flexibility measures such as flexible schedules or remote work, allowing employees to balance their professional and personal responsibilities. Financial and psychological support for employees is also essential, providing resources and assistance to cope with crisis situations or abrupt changes.

5 Conclusion

The three dimensions of commitment - affective, normative, and continuance - were analyzed from the perspective of the owners of these companies in the city of Teresina-PI. The results revealed a unique demographic and occupational profile among the owners, standing out from the parameters commonly used in business management.

This finding reinforces the importance of promoting strategies and practices that stimulate employee commitment, especially in times of crisis and change, such as the post-pandemic context. Companies can adopt flexible approaches, provide appropriate support and resources, and strengthen communication and interpersonal relationships. These results can serve as a basis for the development of effective people management strategies and the strengthening of organizational commitment.

After the Covid-19 pandemic, organizational commitment reviews were conducted with the aim of understanding how companies can ensure the continuity of their activities. Another aspect highlighted in this research is the role of small and medium-sized enterprises in economic development. The research significantly contributes to the scientific knowledge in the field of Management, as Micro and Small Businesses are a universe that allows for very interesting results.

The research has limitations that need to be appreciated. It is not feasible to draw statistical generalizations from the findings. In addition to understanding the obtained results, it is essential to propose practical recommendations based on the research findings. These recommendations can help managers and entrepreneurs promote a more engaged and productive work environment.

Establishing effective communication channels between managers and employees is fundamental. Leaders play a crucial role in promoting organizational commitment. It is essential to create a physically and psychologically safe environment where employees feel valued, respected, and supported. Offering opportunities for growth and professional development is an effective strategy to increase employee commitment.

In a post-pandemic scenario, it is crucial to be open to changes and constantly seek innovative ways of working. Stimulating creativity and entrepreneurial thinking, encouraging the search for solutions and adaptation to new realities. The diversity of perspectives and experiences enriches the team and strengthens employees' identification with the organization.

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